

Rice tungro (RTV) and its vector leafhopper development in synchronized-planting areas

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We studied the epidemiological implications of synchronized rice planting on green leafhopper (GLH) populations and RTV incidence in the 1987 dry season (DS) at Sidenreng Rappang (Sidrap). Integrated RTV management has been implemented in Sidrap. Rice for DS is planted in Nov-Dec and that for the wet season in Apr-May.

Experiments involved five monthly plantings (Oct, Nov, Dec, Jan, Feb) of four varieties (IR26, IR42, IR54, Cisadane) in 10-m² plots in 5 fields, with about 200 m distance between fields. Vector GLH density and RTV incidence were measured.

GLH density in fields planted in Oct and Nov was low (see figure). In the Dec planting, GLH density started to increase 1.5 mo after transplanting and reached a high level in 2-3 mo. GLH in fields planted in Jan and Feb developed similarly.

RTV incidence 56 d after transplanting was high in the Feb planting, lower in the Jan planting, and negligible or zero in the Oct, Nov, and Dec plantings (see figure). Incidence was high in IR42, IR54, and Cisadane,

GLH density every 2 wk and RTV incidence at 56 DT in selected varieties planted monthly Oct 1987-Feb 1988 in Sidrap, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

low in IR26. IR42 was planted in Nov in most surrounding fields and there

High GLH density but low RTV incidence in the Dec planting indicates that GLH density does not always reflect disease incidence. RTV was high in fields established late, after rice in the surrounding fields reached the

flowering stage. In fields planted following the normal planting schedule, RTV infection might occur at late growth stages.

These results confirm the effectiveness of synchronized planting to manage RTV. □

Alternate hosts of rice bacterial blight (BB) pathogen *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

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The rice BB pathogen *X. c.* pv. *oryzae* naturally infects many wild rice species

and some weeds. In India, some of the inoculated weeds have been reported to be already infected.

We raised from seeds in the glasshouse several gramineae species commonly found growing around ricefields. Plant leaves were inoculated with BB pathogen at the three-leaf stage. Leaves were clipped with scissors dipped in a suspension containing actively growing 10⁸ bacterial cells/ml. Infection was

assessed 10 d after inoculation.

In most cases, symptoms appeared as typical water-soaked lesions. Lesions developed rapidly on *Oryza sativa* L., *Cenchrus ciliaris* L., BN2 Bajra-napier hybrid, *Echinochloa crus-galli* L., *Leersia hexandra* Sw., and *Panicum maximum* Jacq. Very small pinhead-like yellowish lesions developed in linear rows on *Brachiaria mutica* Stapf., *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L., and *Cyperus rotundus* L. Six other